

MENADŽMENT PROCESA U VISOKOŠKOLSKIM USTANOVAMA U INDUSTRIJI 5.0

PROCESS MANAGEMENT IN HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS IN INDUSTRY 5.0

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Apstrakt: Industrija 5.0 je društvena promena koja predstavlja razvoj i dostignuća digitalnih tehnologija sa posebnim osvrtom na održivost društva. Ova industrijska revolucija u visokom obrazovanju podrazumeva integrisanje digitalnih tehnologija u nastavni i nenastavni proces visokoškolskih ustanova. Jedan od snažnijih uticaja Industrije 5.0 odražava se na nastavni i nenastavni proces u visokoškolskim ustanovama. U takvim okolnostima menadžment procesa je od ključne važnosti za funkcionisanje i rad visokoškolskih ustanova. S tim u vezi, cilj rada je primena i analiza deskriptivne statistike na ključne varijable u okviru menadžmenta procesa u visokoškolskim ustanovama, imajući u vidu da je nastavni proces primarni proces u visokom obrazovanju. Dobijeni rezultati istraživanja bi mogli poslužiti rukovodstvu visokoškolskih ustanova kao smernice za identifikovanje varijabli koje utiču na performanse procesa u visokoškolskim ustanovama. Rad doprinosi jasnijem sagledavanju performansi procesa u visokoškolskim ustanovama.

Ključne reči: Industrija 5.0, visokoškolske ustanove, menadžment procesa.

Abstract: Industry 5.0 represents a social transformation driven by the development and achievements of digital technologies, with particular emphasis on the sustainability of society. This industrial revolution in higher education involves integrating digital technologies into both teaching and administrative processes within higher education institutions. One of the strongest impacts of Industry 5.0 is evident in these processes. Under such circumstances, process management becomes a key factor for the effective functioning and operation of higher education institutions. Accordingly, the aim of this paper is to apply and analyze descriptive statistics for key variables related to process management in higher education institutions, bearing in mind that the teaching process is the primary process in this context. The obtained research results could serve as guidelines for the management of higher education institutions in identifying variables that influence process performance in higher education. This paper contributes to a clearer understanding of process performance in higher education institutions.

Keywords: Industry 5.0, higher education institutions, process management.

1. INTRODUCTION

The development of digital technologies permeates all spheres of social life and affects every individual. In recent decades, the importance of the digital era has become increasingly significant (Valdés et al., 2021). Digital technologies are constantly evolving (Ferreira et al., 2022), and their application significantly influences organizational success (Valdés et al., 2021). Digital transformation essentially represents digitalization and relies exclusively on the development and achievements of digital technologies. The development of digital technologies extends to all sectors, including higher education (Ferreira et al., 2022). Higher education institutions should follow educational trends such as the adoption and application of digital technologies in the teaching and non-teaching processes (Cerdá Suárez et al., 2021). The industrial revolution known as digital transformation has influenced the improvement of efficiency and effectiveness of operations in all organizations, including higher education institutions. The rapid development of information and communication technologies, along with the development of the internet, has created a social change known as digital transformation (Zhao et al., 2019). Digital transformation represents a digital revolution that enables the creation of innovative higher education, and there is a positive impact of digital technologies on improving the efficiency of the teaching process (Jain et al., 2025). The adoption and application of digital technologies also play a significant role in enhancing competitive advantage (Jackson, 2019). One of the main challenges for leadership in higher education institutions is managing the complexity of both teaching and administrative processes while integrating digital technologies. Higher education institutions that fail to seize the opportunities brought by Industry 5.0 may also miss the benefits it offers (Mian et al., 2020). There is a need for more in-depth research related to the adaptation to Industry 5.0 in higher education institutions (Mian et al., 2020). Furthermore, performance indicators in higher education have not been sufficiently explored, highlighting the need for more comprehensive research on key performance factors within higher education institutions (Stejskal et al., 2020). Similarly, research indicates that although digital technologies are well integrated into higher education, further investigation is needed regarding their application and impact in higher education (Alam & Asimiran, 2021). Accordingly, the research question addressed in this study is: How does process management in higher education institutions affect the implementation of digital technologies within these institutions? Therefore, the aim of the paper is to use research on key variables within process management to present the achievements of Industry 5.0 in higher education institutions. By investigating the factors that influence the adoption of Industry 5.0, this study provides a clearer understanding of its impact on the implementation of digital technologies. Digitalization is known to enhance productivity and improve the efficiency and effectiveness of both teaching and administrative processes in higher education institutions. Considering the gap in the existing literature, this study aims to address unexplored aspects of Industry 5.0 in higher education and its impact on both teaching and administrative processes. The results of

this study may be significant for leadership in higher education institutions by providing a roadmap that highlights the importance of implementing digital technologies. Additionally, the findings can enhance understanding of the performance of both teaching and administrative processes.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Although each country has a specific context for the adoption of digital technologies, most strive to modernize their implementation strategies (Cerdá Suárez et al., 2021). Higher education institutions should adopt digitalization models that best support their strategies, goals, vision, and mission (Valdés et al., 2021).

In 2020, to prevent the spread of COVID-19, nearly all higher education institutions were forced to shift from traditional teaching methods to online learning. The Covid-19 pandemic represents a turning point that marks the digital transformation in higher education (Abumalloh et al., 2021). Online education became the only method of delivering the teaching process (Abumalloh et al., 2021). Higher education institutions had to adapt to the new situation, facing numerous challenges that the new method of teaching delivery brought.

Digital transformation in higher education requires a systematic approach, meaning it should be integrated into all aspects of operations within the business processes of higher education institutions (Cerdá Suárez et al., 2021). The transition to digital education has prompted the digital transformation of higher education (Cerdá Suárez et al., 2021). It is defined as the process of integrating digital technologies into all dimensions of teaching and non-teaching processes, encompassing the development of skills and competencies necessary for the effective use of digital technologies (Valdés et al., 2021). Digital transformation also implies a shift in the way educational services are delivered, moving from traditional methods to online education. Consequently, it can influence the knowledge economy (Hill & Lawton, 2018). The application of digital technologies in higher education is particularly significant for national development, especially in developing countries (Alam & Asimiran, 2021). Furthermore, the adoption and implementation of digital technologies can affect the sustainability of operations within higher education institutions.

Digital transformation in higher education can also have a significant impact on the orientation of society (Taimur & Onuki, 2022). Although digital technologies had already been applied in higher education institutions prior to the Covid-19 pandemic—particularly in developed countries—the pandemic is considered a turning point for higher education (Nurhas et al., 2021). The use of digital technologies was more widespread in other service sectors than in higher education institutions. According to Arnold et al. (2021) and others, investment in technological capacity is a key factor for organizations, including higher education institutions, in both developed and developing

countries. Given that the teaching process is the primary activity of higher education institutions, investment in the development and infrastructure of digital technologies is of crucial importance for their leadership.

3. BUSINESS PROCESS MANAGEMENT IN HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS IN THE DIGITAL ERA

In the digital era, business process management is of key importance. This is because traditional (analog) business processes are being transformed into digital ones (Cerdá Suárez et al., 2021). Within higher education institutions, the primary business process is the teaching process. This means that digital technologies should be integrated into the teaching process. However, besides the teaching process, investment in the non-teaching process as well as the research process is also very important. Business processes represent a set of interconnected activities that transform input elements into outputs. For the improvement of the teaching process, it is very important that digital technologies are well integrated with the teaching process as the primary process of the higher education institution. The adoption and application of digital technologies in the teaching and non-teaching processes could contribute to cost reduction (Ghemawat, 2017). This cost reduction can be analyzed from the perspectives of both higher education institutions and students.

The leadership of higher education institutions must establish effective strategies for managing both teaching and non-teaching processes, with a primary focus on enhancing student satisfaction. The application of digital technologies in higher education can be an alternative for the future, by establishing the best strategies that will serve to meet the demands primarily of students, but also of other relevant stakeholders (Arnold et al., 2021). Decision-makers in higher education should also consider students' access to digital equipment as a key factor for the successful implementation of online education (Muflih et al., 2021). Some authors, such as Lacka et al. (2021), point out that there is a lack of research on the representation of digital technologies in higher education.

4. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The structure of the variables used in this research was taken in its original form from the ISO 9004:2018 standard, that is, the guidelines for achieving sustainable success. The research included public and private higher education institutions in Serbia and its surrounding region. The technique used for data collection in the research was a questionnaire. The structure of the sample consisted primarily of teaching staff, but also included relevant non-teaching, administrative, staff employed in student services and other departments connected to the teaching process. The demographic structure of the questionnaire consisted of four items, while six items referred to the performance of process management in the context of Industry 5.0 in higher education institutions. The distribution of the questionnaire was carried out via email. The analyzed variables of

process management were assessed using a Likert scale from 1 to 5. The research identified key variables within process management in higher education institutions. A total of 374 correctly completed responses were collected. By analyzing descriptive statistics, the performance of process management variables in higher education institutions in the context of the application of digital technologies was observed. In this sense, the questions used in this research were as follows (MP_1 – MP_6): how are the processes that are significant for Industry 5.0 defined; how are the processes that are significant for Industry 5.0 managed; how are responsibilities and authorities for the processes that are significant for Industry 5.0 established; how are the relationships between the processes that are significant for Industry 5.0 managed; how is the improvement of the performance of the processes that are significant for Industry 5.0 evaluated; and how is the achieved level of performance of the processes that are significant for Industry 5.0 maintained?

5. RESEARCH RESULTS

Analyzing the demographic structure of the respondents, it was determined that the study included 176 male and 198 female participants. Then, based on age, 29 respondents are up to 30 years old, 94 respondents are between 31 and 40 years old, 124 respondents are between 41 and 50 years old, 88 respondents are between 51 and 60 years old, while 39 respondents are over 60 years old. Analyzing the positions within the higher education institution, 268 professors participated in the research, 63 teaching assistants, and 63 respondents employed in administrative services. Analyzing the structure of founders of higher education institutions, the study predominantly included institutions founded by the state, while only 35 higher education institutions had private individuals as founders.

In addition to the analysis of demographic data, descriptive statistics were performed. Descriptive statistics is the analysis of the characteristics of a data sample (Fisher & Marshall, 2009). The primary role of descriptive statistical analysis is to better understand the description of the characteristics of a data set. Also, the role of this analysis is to describe the sample for data analysis (Fisher & Marshall, 2009). This type of statistical analysis allows insight into the distribution of data based on the sample (Frankfort-Nachmias & Nachmias, 2008). Furthermore, this analysis describes the relationships between variables, which also represents the first step in research (Kaur et al., 2018).

Based on this analysis, researchers are enabled to gain insight into the characteristics of the data. Descriptive statistics provide researchers with insight into numerical data, which is very important for understanding the analysis of the entire data set. Based on this statistical analysis, it is possible to clearly and very simply observe the relationships between the observed variables. The measures used within descriptive statistics are: arithmetic mean, mode, median, standard deviation, minimum, maximum, and percentage distribution. These measures represent the foundation for future statistical

analyses within quantitative research (Cooksey, 2020; Mishra et al., 2019; Thompson, 2009; Kaur et al., 2018). Table 1 shows the descriptive statistical analysis for the process management variables in the context of Industry 5.0.

Table 1: Descriptive statistics

Variables	Item	Mean	Std. Deviation	Median	Mode	Range
Process Definition	MP_1	3,17	1,065	3,00	3	4
Process Management	MP_2	3,16	1,077	3,00	3	4
Establishing Responsibilities and Authorities for Processes	MP_3	3,14	1,116	3,00	3	4
Managing the Relationships Between Processes	MP_4	3,13	1,105	3,00	3	4
Improving Process Performance	MP_5	3,22	1,089	3,00	3	4
Maintaining the Achieved Level of Process Performance	MP_6	3,15	1,055	3,00	3	4

Source: the authors' research

In addition, the Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) test for measuring adequacy was analyzed, with a value of 0.935, which is in accordance with Williams et al. (2010), while the Cronbach's Alpha test was used to measure internal consistency, with a value of 0.960. According to Cronbach (1951), values of 0.70 and above confirm the reliability of the measurement instrument.

6. DISCUSSION

In Table 1, the values range from 3.13 to 3.22, indicating no significant fluctuations in the respondents' attitudes. The standard deviation values range from 1.055 to 1.116. The median and mode values are both 3, while the range is 4 for all research questions. Analyzing these values, it can be summarized that respondents least agree with the statement regarding the management of relationships between processes, whereas the highest-rated variable concerns the improvement of process performance, which aligns with the findings of Yeung (2018). Processes are specific to each organization and largely depend on the nature of their operations. The observed results likely reflect the specificity of higher education institutions. Higher education involves sensitive and complex processes, among which the teaching process is particularly prominent (Falch et al., 2022). Within higher education, the process perspective is considered crucial for the sustainability of society (Al-Bahi et al., 2021). Measuring process performance is especially significant for higher education institutions because these performances directly impact the outcomes for relevant stakeholders (Stejskal et al., 2020). Further analysis indicated that the obtained KMO test value for sampling adequacy is 0.935,

which is considered appropriate and consistent with the recommendations of Hair et al. (2014) and Williams et al. (2010).

CONCLUSION

The aim of the paper was to identify variables within process management and to examine key aspects using descriptive statistical analysis in the context of Industry 5.0 in higher education institutions in Serbia and its region. Based on the study's objective, it can be concluded that, for the leadership of higher education institutions, it is crucial to establish strategies that meet the demands of students and other relevant stakeholders. Additionally, the integration of digital technologies is essential for improving both teaching and non-teaching processes in higher education institutions, primarily to enhance the efficiency and effectiveness of the teaching process, which is the primary process in these institutions (Ghemawat, 2017). Organizational systems should periodically implement monitoring and measurement of processes to further improve their efficiency and effectiveness (Filipović & Đurić, 2010).

Future research may include additional relevant variables, such as resource management in the context of Industry 5.0. Moreover, future studies could focus on other geographic areas, given the lack of research on the application of digital technologies within Industry 5.0. This aligns with the conclusions of many authors who emphasize that it remains unclear whether this industrial revolution is uniformly implemented worldwide, and to what extent it is represented across organizational systems, including higher education institutions

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